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Development of entrepreneurial education for engineers

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INTRODUCTION

Enterprises are fundamental for the societies. They offer employment and the state gains tax assets based on salaries paid to employees. Most enterprises are micro enterprises or small and medium-sized enterprises – SMEs – and they are growing more than the big ones. A big part of the SMEs are technology-based. In Finland 70 % of the industrial companies produce and sell innovative products [1]. It is necessary that also SMEs achieve and export competitive products. Especially the successful technology products are important. Generally spoken, the trade balance should be positive. A country and its companies should have more sales than purchases. New, vital, technology-based businesses are needed to make it possible. Therefore new capable business-oriented engineers are needed. The role of universities of applied sciences is important because they educate engineers, who are the main professionals especially in SMEs, who develop products and business. This is the basis to the fact that universities of applied sciences need to offer more education especially in entrepreneurship to engineering students.

The main focus in engineering education is on technology but it is not enough to have capacity to carry out the product development and the production. Additionally the products must be taken to the market. From an idea to the market there is a long multiphase pathway to pass. To arrange this complex chain of actions, an enterprise is needed. In technology-based industry, the convenient background for an entrepreneur is engineering degree. S/he has an adequate education in order to understand the technology that fulfills the needs of clients. Still, additionally, understanding of the technology market and business is needed.

This research report includes a literature review about entrepreneurial education of engineers. Also, the result of questioning to engineers who have taken the engineer degree is presented. They have given a statement about the education and made proposals to improve it. It is rare to find this kinds of research reports. Additionally, this paper discusses the characters of potential engineering students and the educational approach of the universities to train successful entrepreneurs of the technology field.

This research is a part of series of small researches to prepare a wider research about entrepreneur skills, education and achievements of engineers graduated especially from a university of applied sciences.

1 GENERAL

1.1 Technology-based companies

All the start-ups do not survive up to a stable growth stage and therefore there should be a large number of start-ups so that some of them would continue their existence for a longer time. The companies have to survive the start and first years after finding an idea and the first development stage. In most cases the engineers are trained to implement technical product development but not enough to take care of the marketing and the entire business. Capable entrepreneurs are the ones who make it happen. They are economic visionaries fueling economic growth [2]. A large part of successful enterprises are based on technology products or services and they are important because they have possibilities to design, produce and market the products to export. The role of engineers as professionals and managers of those companies is crucial. Many research reports discuss the technology aspect of the engineering education but a minority discusses the entrepreneurial education. On the other hand a general business education that is not focusing on any specific industrial sector is a popular subject in researches. Concerning the technology-based companies, the more advanced the used technology is, the more often the founder of the company is an engineer.

1.2 Role of engineers

During the last decades the need to offer entrepreneurial education for engineers has been discussed more and more. Universities of applied sciences have a big role in teaching engineers to work in SMEs. They can become entrepreneurs immediately after their graduations or after a period as an employee in a business of another entrepreneur.

Often a technology-based business produces and sells physical products. In order to have a successful product, good ideas have to be found. These ideas are evaluated and the best one is chosen. The process is long from the idea to the product that provides profit on the market. It includes many different phases. The idea is further processed in product development. Thereafter it is ready for production. Simultaneously the marketing is planned and prepared. Once the product has been launched on the market it still is under constant further development based on reactions and needs of customers. Additionally, during this process many details of management and leadership as well as legal issues and contacts with public administration have to be taken care off. Normally, in universities the education of this process is divided into different subjects and disciplines. It means that different students are educated for different stages of the pathway of the product process – engineers for technology stages and students of marketing and economics for other stages. In traditional education one person does not learn the entire holistic chain which is needed in real business. This is the main problem in education and causes difficulties in setting up and developing technology-based companies.

The big companies have better chances of employing people who have been trained especially to certain special tasks because there are enough special tasks for full time professionals. In SMEs and especially in starting start-ups the entrepreneurs has to take care of everything. They have to know what special knowledge is needed and where it can be acquired. They have to be able to communicate with other specialists effectively. In this

case the holistic general education is better but at the same time there has to be a strong technological base in order to understand the technology of the product and production. Also, it is necessary to understand the situation of the client who is often using the product in a technical environment. A suitable person for this position is a business-oriented engineer who has been educated in the right way.

1.3 Role of universities of applied sciences

The role of universities is to provide the companies in the area with professionals who possess right skills and knowledge. That is why the universities have to be aware of the circumstances where the graduated engineers will work as entrepreneurs. Universities of applied sciences are very suitable players in educating entrepreneurs into the technology industry. The main focus is not on preparing students for a researcher career but more on practical design and production. The mental attitude is to achieve practical results effectively. The amount, method and content of the entrepreneurial education of a university depend on its strategy. Because traditionally the focus is on technology, there has not always been attention and interest to include entrepreneurship in the curricula. The universities of applied sciences have good possibilities to take a bigger role in developing entrepreneurship in their operating areas. Business-oriented engineering education does not need necessarily to lead to entrepreneurship but it is also good if it leads to an entrepreneurial attitude mode to work inside a company as an employee. This kind of behavior has been widely called intrapreneurship.

2 OBJECT AND METHODOLOGY

The purpose of this research was to find grounds for entrepreneurial engineering education and to suggest means to enhance it. Firstly the characters of successful young entrepreneurs are discussed. The second topic is to conduct an inquiry to engineers who have graduated from universities of applied sciences and academic universities into the perception of their education according to the readiness to the entrepreneurship. The research has been made from the point of view of an experienced engineer. The third topic is how to arrange a convenient entrepreneurial education inside the engineering education in a university of applied sciences.

The approach of this research was to make a literature review and to make an inquiry and an interview directed to engineer-entrepreneurs who have graduated from universities of applied sciences. Also, the extra-curriculum events are presented that have been realized in Oulu University of Applied Sciences as well as experiences of them.

In this report proposals for entrepreneurial education in universities of applied sciences are presented. This study is a part of the study series which have been made from different points of view to the entrepreneurial education in Oulu University of Applied Sciences (OUAS). It is a continuation to the paper presented in SEFI2015.

3 LITERATURE REVIEW

3.1 Traits of nascent entrepreneurship

Nascent entrepreneurs are people who are actively trying to set up their own businesses. Determination of these people is not easy. Characteristics of an entrepreneur have been presented in several research reports. Creativity, innovativeness, tenacity, risk-taking, team

building capacity, customer orientation, contact with marketing, project engagement are often mentioned [2], [3], [4], [5], [6].

The features can be classified into human and social capital. Human capital is e.g. creativity, innovativeness, tenacity, risk-taking. Social capital is a capacity to get in contact with other people and to work with different kinds of people. Team building capability is important in entrepreneurship. St-Jean et al [7] have written about the differences based on psychological, sociocultural and economic factors influencing entrepreneurial intentions.

Young entrepreneurs use bootstrapping and effectuation mechanisms to compensate the lack of knowledge, experience and financial capital that more experienced entrepreneurs have in use. They also benefit of social support from their parents and other entrepreneurial family members and friends. They are active in participating all kinds of small-scale ventures and senior managers of the established companies are arranging access to additional opportunities. By using their creativity, energy and originality the young entrepreneurs acquire the experiences and the contacts they need for their next development steps to develop their entrepreneurship. Social skills are important when supporters are looked for especially in the first stage along the pathway towards a skilled and successful entrepreneurship. According to Cannone et al [8], young successful entrepreneurs are investing heavily on their social capital to countervail the effect of the young age.

Dietz et al [9] have discussed the management of the complexity. Surroundings of the enterprise is changing continuously and the entrepreneur has to react to that. This situation is connected to the ability to tolerate uncertainty, and surely asks for tenacity.

An entrepreneurial engineer has been discussed by Elia et al [10]. Human capital means that s/he is capable of matching technology innovation with business challenges and societal development, assuring economical, technological and environmental sustainability.

Garsia et al [6] address to design work as a positive skill for an entrepreneur. That approach enables entrepreneurs to be pro-active, consistent and reliable, rather than just exploratory and reactive. Design possesses instruments that allow framing, development, co-designing and prototyping complex intangible projects. In their education engineers learn this kind of way to work. They have got used to thinking analytically.

3.2 Education of entrepreneurship

The manner to arrange engineering education has developed along a century. When the great technology inventions appeared and technology was taken into use in bigger scale, the need for the technological engineering skills has been obvious. The need for new technological products has been urgent. Production has been a bottleneck. Later, during and especially in the end of the 1900's the businesses have faced an increasing global competition. That has caused a need to find new competitive products in order to obtain revenue. The marketing effort has become more important than before. Still, in these days the engineering education promotes for students wage-employment rather than self-employment like Wani et al [2] have stated in their report discussing techno-entrepreneurial workforce.

In most universities in the engineering education the entrepreneurship has been superficially dealt with. This is understandable because the focus is on technology and normally the educators have a long experience as technology experts in companies but only a few have

an entrepreneurial background. According to a research [11], 5 % of the teachers of OUAS have pursued an entrepreneurial career. In many cases the teachers and university managers who have the same technology background are developing the education and naturally the focus is on technology. In the strategy of the university the development of entrepreneurship is mentioned. The first steps are taken e.g. by offering one basic course in entrepreneurship for all students. Additionally, there is a possibility for students to develop their business ideas in the business incubator where the entrepreneurship is profoundly dealt with.

Baumol [12] has discussed in his report the level and direction of education in the USA and compared it with the education in other countries. He presents that the level of subjects like physics, mathematics, technical and scientific disciplines of the American students in elementary schools and high schools is clearly at a lower level compared with some European and Asian countries. Yet, American students make more dissertations and the attitude and ability to make start-ups is higher. This is a paradox but Baumol [12] presents that maybe the educational approaches that provide effectively the mastery of the extant body of intellectual material actually tend to handicap a student's ability to "think out of the box" and prevents to find new groundbreaking ideas and breakthrough approaches.

3.3 Attraction of entrepreneurial education

How the interest in the entrepreneurship can be aroused? Fellnhofer et al [13] have studied the influence of the role model on perceived entrepreneurial desirability and feasibility. They have found that embedding entrepreneurial role models in education promote entrepreneurial activities. When students have a possibility to become acquainted with real entrepreneur's careers, it creates a positive awareness. Furthermore, the development of the right identity can be achieved with the help of the relevant peer groups. Also, they have stated that in addition to the entrepreneurial knowledge and skills that have been studied in a traditional way, the creation of the entrepreneurial identity is essential for the acting as an entrepreneur. The authors have noticed that entrepreneurial education contributes the entrepreneurial feasibility. Hence, as a conclusion it can be said that a role model of an experienced and successful entrepreneur connected to entrepreneurial education is an essential combination to stimulate the right attitude. According to a questionnaire to bachelor students of engineering, 31 % have a serious intent to found an enterprise in the future [11].

4 ENTREPRENEURIAL EDUCATION IN OUAS

In the strategy statement of OUAS entrepreneurial education is mentioned. It means that all curricula include at least one basic course in entrepreneurship. The size of the course is two credits. Additionally, a business incubator is available. If a student has an idea, s/he can make a business plan of it. The scope of the subject is 10 credits.

Every year a business idea contest Kickstart is arranged. There students can present their business ideas and receive guidance to develop them further. The next step is the choice of 10 best ideas which are prepared to be presented to the jury. The members of the jury are from businesses and banks. After a short presentations the best idea is chosen and awarded with 1500 euros. As a result of this extra-curriculum education principle, a few promising start-ups have been found. They are in a growing stage and they have received a significant risk financing for the further development and growth. A part of the entrepreneurial education is a yearly realized entrepreneur afternoon where former graduates from OUAS present their career paths as entrepreneurs. Students have been very interested in those events and they have had an opportunity to discuss the interesting matters with the entrepreneurs. These

events have caused demand to participate in the studies in the business incubator. The entrepreneurs have had a very positive attitude to meet students and to tell them about entrepreneurship. A phenomenon of the role model presented by Fellnhofer et al [13] has been easily seen.

An international project to develop innovation and entrepreneurial education together with enterprises is being prepared. The idea is that student groups in universities in different countries carry out a product process from the idea to the market. The groups will be guided together by university teachers, business professionals and entrepreneurs. The aim is that students get a realistic and holistic impression of the innovation process and of the entrepreneurship.

5 QUESTIONING AND INTERVIEWS

5.1 Questionings to entrepreneurs

The questioning was directed to 12 entrepreneurs who have an engineering degree. They had 1 – 30 years experience of the entrepreneurship. The interviewees reacted positively to the entrepreneurial education to the engineering students. They thought of the society as a whole and they expressed that the region and entire society needed more new enterprises to provide economic welfare. The first of the main findings was that the entrepreneurs emphasised economics, business strategy, management and marketing as useful entrepreneurial subjects as part of engineering education. Entrepreneurs were asked about the number of student who should be trained to the entrepreneurship. All of them mentioned that an entrepreneurial education should be offered to 100 % of the students. That would be important even though students would not act as entrepreneurs but would work as intrapreneurs in companies owned by someone else.

The second finding was the willingness of entrepreneurs to participate in the planning and executing of the entrepreneurial education supporting the actual teachers. According to the opinions of the questioned entrepreneurs, the engineering education should include case presentations carried out by active entrepreneurs. They are ready to come and present their companies and their experiences to students. The third interesting finding was that the share of 30 % of entrepreneurs and business development professionals proposed the mentoring of young nascent and active entrepreneurs and the presentation of the role model of an SME-entrepreneur. Also, it came out in the interviews that most of the contacted professionals emphasized the encouragement of the nascent entrepreneurial students to continue the studies towards the entrepreneurship.

5.2 Business development organisations

The proposal of the representatives of the local business development organisations was that it is beneficial to present to students the companies that are for sale. The experienced entrepreneurs want to give the companies to younger generations. There are a numerous micro and small enterprises for sale. By becoming acquainted with them, the nascent entrepreneurs learn practical issues about business.

6 RESULTS AND PROPOSALS

In the following the proposals to develop the entrepreneurial engineering education are presented. They are based on the literature review, the questioning of entrepreneurship and the interview that was made to the entrepreneurs and to the business development specialists.

According to the former research, 31 % of the engineering students already have had a business idea in their minds but they have not made any actions to start a start-up [11]. In order to identify the nascent entrepreneurs and to support their path to the entrepreneurship, a clear organized system needs to be developed. In the beginning of the studies events can be arranged together with entrepreneurs where the identification can take place. Thereafter, they can be activated and encouraged to participate in the tentative entrepreneurial courses. [14]. In the later education it is important to offer firstly solid skills and knowledge about technology, secondly a formal set of activities to found a start-up, and thirdly it is convenient to strengthen the human and social abilities and personal attributes such as risk perception and self-efficacy [14], [12].

The best alternative is a separate study line for the entrepreneurially oriented students. For them it is advantageous to learn the entire product process, the chain of actions which is needed on the pathway from the idea up to the market. It is not only technology that is needed but also actions in management, marketing, financing, strategic decisions, etc.

Normally, the development of curricula and education methods are realized by teachers. Because the entrepreneurs are ready to support in this work, it is beneficial to create a collaboration method. Also, when recruiting teachers the entrepreneurial background of the candidates is worth taking into consideration. Connected to the collaboration with entrepreneurs, the mentoring of the entrepreneurially oriented students is one effective mean to support the emerging business career as also Hulsink has discussed [14]. In this connection it is possible to present to students the role model of senior entrepreneurs as well.

The conclusion of the research is that the role of the universities is important when the know-how of engineers to create and manage technology-based companies is developed. In engineering education it is possible and worth realizing the motivation of the nascent entrepreneurs together with entrepreneurs who have made engineering degree.

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